

What Is a National Observatory?

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Astronomy is rooted in phenomenology. Discoveries constitute the blood; studies of well-defined samples, the shoulder; and surveys, the backbone. Astronomy is perhaps the most capital-intensive field, when normalized by the size of the professional community. Along with biology, astronomy is a leader in Big Data. “Astroinformatics” is now a major area in our field.

While large telescopes dominate our budget, the phenomenological nature of our subject requires not only a range of facilities but also a diverse and wide user base. Instrumentation enables discovery and is therefore vital. A case that addresses some of these points is the Kitt Peak 84-inch telescope, which was not a big telescope even at first light (1964) but is notable for the discovery of the first pulsating white dwarf (1969), the Lyman-alpha forest (1971), and the first gravitational lens (1979).

National organizations (e.g., NRAO) were created to build and manage facilities that lie beyond the grasp of even well-endowed radio groups. In order to articulate a future vision for a US National Observatory for optical and infrared (OIR) astronomy, we need to go back to the turn of the last century. The US was dominated by privately funded observatories that achieved spectacular successes—the determination of the size of our Galaxy, the discovery of the expansion of the Universe, the discovery of Pluto, and the cosmological origin of quasars.

However, this model has reached its limit. The Rockefeller Foundation gift of \$6M to Caltech for the 200-inch

telescope corresponded to a 57 ppm (parts per million) fraction of the FY1929 US GDP. The Keck Foundation gift(s) to Caltech for the two 10m telescopes was 28 ppm (circa FY1990), matched by contributions from the University of California for operations and instrumentation. It appears to me that 30 ppm is an upper limit for purely philanthropic funding of telescope facilities.

Nonetheless, a National Observatory is needed when flagship facilities cross the billion-dollar mark. However, for maximum national benefit, a National Observatory and the existing university-based observatories have to work together, complementing their strengths and minimizing their weaknesses. One should never minimize the role of universities in the training of the next generation of astronomers and instrumentalists.

Here is my vision for NSF’s NOIRLab. It must, like ESO (Paranal), deliver high-performance and reliable state-of-art telescopes. NOIRLab must be able to deploy all of its assets to address ambitious projects (e.g., follow-up facilities working in tandem with Vera C. Rubin Observatory). Next, NOIRLab has to provide facilities for specialized telescopes (at Kitt Peak and Cerro Tololo) and be the steward for nurturing technological developments that are key to our field. Finally, noting the rise of trans-national projects such as ALMA, SKA, and ELT, NOIRLab must therefore be fully empowered by the US astronomical community to energetically represent the US in such projects.

University groups are well situated to lead astroinformatics and to develop new methodologies, including detectors. Universities must have stable access to federal funding to build ever more powerful instruments for all state-of-the art telescopes. The more ambitious groups can build public-private mid-scale facilities (e.g., NIR/narrow band/polarimetric synoptic surveys, massively multiplexed spectroscopic facilities) and even consider strategic partnerships with NOIRLab for mutual gains.

Failure to form and execute an ambitious Universities–NOIRLab plan will weaken the global standing of US ground-based OIR astronomy.